

METHODOLOGY OF USING BLENDED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN TRAINING PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Annotation: The strategy of modernization of education at the present stage, the creation of a new information educational space, the use of global network technologies at all levels of education predetermined the requirement to increase the level of methodological training of a teacher who is ready to use new information technologies in his professional activities. The need to include modern pedagogical technologies that form the student's online culture in the training of specialists at the university becomes important. Learning technology, combining network learning with face-to-face learning, integrating traditional forms with electronic technologies is one of such technologies. The purpose of the work is to justify the relevance of the use of mixed learning technology for the implementation of the task of methodical training of a primary school teacher. The research discloses some of the advantages of using the "work area change" model of mixed learning technology in teacher training. We justified our position in the organization of the process of forming the methodological competence of the future teacher with the use of mixed learning technology. We illustrated the use of a professionally oriented method of organizing students' activities, aimed at applying information technologies when future teachers master mathematical and methodological content, with an example of classes organizing in the course "Theory and Technologies of Primary Mathematical Education" in the form of a web quest.

Keywords: mixed training; change of work areas methodical competence; information technologies; primary teacher.

Blended learning is an educational approach that combines traditional lessons with a teacher with distance learning, where the student controls the pace of learning. In face-to-face classes, children learn communication, form models of thinking and behavior, and during independent studies, they develop planning and control skills, learn to manage their time and search for information. Blended learning technology combines the advantages of face-to-face and distance learning at school and compensates for their disadvantages.

Of course, labor education occupies a special place in the upbringing of a comprehensively developed personality. This subject is mental and physical work for students. It serves educational purposes, such as creating a broad understanding of the types and processes of labor, as well as developing labor-related skills and qualifications.

Modern information technologies penetrate all spheres of human activity and form a global information space that influences all aspects of society. These processes require modernization of education at all its levels. The achievement of this goal is facilitated by the creation of a new information educational space, which assumes the possibility of choosing new approaches to organizing the educational process and implementing new learning technologies.

A related problem is the training at the university's pedagogical departments - the problem of updating the forms, methods and means of training in the process of forming the methodological competence of future teachers in the Internet environment. The use of information technologies in higher education is aimed at improving the quality of training specialists through the use of active and interactive teaching methods; the use of digital technologies in the educational process that are close to modern youth; increasing the creative and intellectual components of educational activities; personalization of training, taking into account the individual characteristics of students; ensuring the possibility of choosing an individual learning path; integration of various types of educational activities; the possibility of improving the educational process through the use of virtual laboratories, virtual excursions, etc.

There are several models of blended learning. In my practice, I use three models: "Flipped Classroom", "Station Rotation", "Autonomous Group".

Active use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, increasing the effectiveness of training, analysis and implementation in practice is one of the important tasks of our time. Primary education is the main link in the comprehensive school in this regard, it is necessary to pay more attention to the perfect development of the student's personality in this process. The responsibilities of primary school teachers are limitless. They accustom schoolchildren who have just stepped on the threshold of school to school life and open the way for them to receive a modern education. During this period, children's attitude to learning and mental potential are formed. This also shows that the task of primary school teachers is responsible. Classes organized on the basis of pedagogical technologies should meet the needs of the student in terms of organization methods and methods of delivery. Because such classes are closer to the child's psyche. In the education system, the term "innovative" is understood as the introduction of innovations into the goal and content of education, a new approach, the organization of activities in the interaction of the teacher and the student, the process of improving pedagogical technologies, as well as the process of improving pedagogical technologies. a set of methods, forms and means of teaching.

Today, "instead of forcing students to study the same old program to pass an exam, it is more important to improve their mental attitude by applying various new and innovative ideas. A teaching method that focuses on, simply put, modern learning." methods.

The existing methods do not work very effectively with the new generation of students. Standardized education does not take into account the individual qualities of the child and the need for creative growth. Despite a number of problems that cannot be solved by old methods, there are difficulties in introducing innovations. The teacher must understand that introducing innovative methods not only helps students learn the material more effectively, but also develops their creative potential. But it also helps the teacher realize his intellectual and creative potential.

In recent years, the amount of knowledge in science and technology has increased dramatically, and human ability to adapt to new knowledge in science and technology has also increased. Therefore, there is a great need for innovative and creative minds to explore the unknown and undiscovered areas of various fields. Adopting modern methods to cope with the modern world and the era of high technology is the only way to stay strong in the developed world. Modern teaching is undoubtedly the need of the times because of its relevance in modern times. The revolution in science and technology requires great ideas and

all-round efforts to overcome any situation that arises along the way. All this is on the small shoulders of great students. Therefore, it is very important not only to impart knowledge to students but also to improve their skills.

Blended learning is not focused on the classical preparation of a student who masters a certain set of knowledge, but on the development of the ability to independently search for the necessary information and creatively approach solving complex problems. Therefore, each mentor asks the question, with the help of which methodology will students learn the necessary amount of material with a sufficient share of independent effort in order to achieve the greatest effect.

Scientists have developed various educational methods, which are based on approaches that differ from each other depending on specialization. For example, the systems of developmental learning of L.V. Zankov, D.B. Elkonin, V.V. Davydov, humane pedagogy of Sh.A. Amonashvili, principles of personality-oriented education of I.S. Yakimanskaya. All these generally diverse concepts are united by the need to combine the following ideas:

- an activity-based approach to learning aimed at stimulating the active participation of the student in the process of acquiring knowledge;
- formation of an educational environment in which the student develops skills of independence and realizes personal responsibility for decision-making;
- creation of an atmosphere of mutual trust and respect between the teacher and the student;
- the system of objective control of the students' success should develop in them the ability to self-assess, which increases the level of educational activity;
- the learning process should cause satisfaction with the results and experience positive emotions upon reaching intermediate stages without signs of any coercion.

In this case, the tasks are accompanied by educational videos and a variety of creative exercises on various topics. After studying this or that material, at the end you can conduct an online test, which will help the teacher identify the strengths and weaknesses of the students and take them into account in further training..

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